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INSIDE

Editorial	
BJP's Predicament	5
<i>B.K.</i>	
What ails India's Global Educational Ranking?	7
<i>Anil Singh</i>	
Sino-Sri Lanka Relations and India's Security	17
<i>Puja Bansal</i>	
Tax Revenue <i>vis-à-vis</i>	
Public Revenue in India	24
<i>Dr. Stanly Joseph P & Prarthna P</i>	
FDI and Exports in India: An Overview	28
<i>Dr. C.Prabu</i>	
Women and Media	31
<i>Deepan Das</i>	
Ethical Perspective of Women towards	
Environment	35
<i>Mrs.S.Velanganni & Mrs. M. A. Barveen</i>	
<i>Dr. D. Jeba Selvi Anitha</i>	
How Timothy Leary Changed America?	38
<i>Eddie J. Girdner</i>	
Democratic Aspects of Kebang	
System of the Misings	45
<i>Dr. Nabo Kumar Pegu</i>	
Issues and Strategies in Digital Preservation	52
<i>V. Harineeswaran</i>	

What ails India's Global Educational Ranking?

Anil Singh*

[India has one of the largest higher education systems in the world. Over the past few years, India's higher education sector has witnessed tremendous growth. The sector boasts of 44 central universities, 298 state universities, 148 state private universities, 130 deemed universities, 82 MHRD funded technical institutions including IITs, IIMs, IISERs, etc. While India has shown impressive growth in the number of institutes and enrolment in the country, it still faces challenges on several fronts including low and inequitable access to higher education, shortage of faculty, deficient infrastructure as well as low-quality and inadequate research.]

It seems that entire Indian Higher education system is going through a crisis of identity. While delivering convocation addresses of various universities and educational institutions, President Pranab Mukherjee also expressed deep concern over the poor quality of higher education, and said that institutes in the country have failed to claim international repute like those enjoyed by Oxford, Harvard or Stanford universities and attributed this to the poor quality of education, vacant teaching posts and lack of competitiveness among centres of excellence.

The three most widely observed university rankings – Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings, Times Higher Education World University Rankings powered by Thomson Reuters and the Academic Ranking of World Universities commonly known as Shanghai Ranking – have published their result of 2014 and none of the Indian educational institution could get the place in top 200. Naturally a pertinent question appears why our national elite institutions are not within the top rankings, whereas many universities from other Asian countries have got better ranks than us.

Considering that India is one of the global emerging and knowledge dependent economies, it is a serious concern in terms of quality of advance education that is being offered by our universities. To get the place in global ranking, there are many issues which need immediate attention by our educational

planners and policy makers to revamp our education system before it is too late. Some of them are discussed in this paper.

Teaching an unattractive profession

The educational system of India has not been able to attract meritorious students in teaching and research. For the past fifteen to twenty years, interest in teaching profession has been declining and it has not been opted as a first choice as career by the students. Due to attractive pay and perks, our best talent is attracted towards MNCs and other private sector jobs and second choice is government civil services.

Then remaining students want to join teaching profession. If we conduct survey at the level of Assistant Professor, we will find that mostly joined this profession by chance and not by choice. To make this profession more attractive, we have to start Indian Education Service (IES) at par with other central services like IAS, IFS, and IPS for which selection should be done by Union Public Service Commission (UPSC). In many states of India there is State Education Service to select Assistant Professor through their respective Public Service Commissions.

Shortage of Qualified Teachers

The strength of an institution is its human resource. It has been amply realized that the way faculty is recruited leaves much to be desired. The moment any faculty position is advertised, a sort of rat race and lobbying starts. All of us are aware of these

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facts and need to be candid about accepting them. Recruitment of poor faculty has a cascade effect on the overall health of the institutions as well as on the human resource they generate by way of education and research.

It has been seen that non-meritorious, mediocre and predetermined candidates are entering in teaching profession through unfair means. In most of the cases, subject experts do not give their frank opinion on the performance and domain knowledge of the candidate. They merely attend the interview to fulfill the quorum. Chairpersons dominate the whole interview board. Fresh appointments at the level of Assistant Professor are not done on a transparent basis especially in autonomous bodies.

Due to lack of standard guidelines for screening, stronger candidates are screened out deliberately to make way for pre-determined candidates. For example, at the entry level for Assistant Professor the essential qualification is Post graduation with UGC-NET. When number of candidates for the post is very large, screening is carried out keeping in mind the qualification of favourite candidate. There are no standard criteria fixed by the UGC regarding number of candidates to be called against one post.

There are many universities in India which have been running various regular and professional courses for so many years without appointing any regular faculty. These courses are being taught by contractual teachers on *ad-hoc* or per period basis. Now we can imagine as to what type of teaching standard these universities have and how can these universities compete at global level?

A new practice started in this profession is to declare the interview result as “NFS” which means “None Found Suitable”. Such types of cases have been seen in many interviews where there is no favourable candidate of the Chairperson of the interview board. There are no defined criteria of suitability. It is just a matter of interpretation.

Lack of Regular Curriculum up-gradation

While addressing the first-ever conference of Directors of National Institutes of Technology (NIT) on November 07, 2013, President Pranab

Mukherjee said at least one or two departments in every NIT must be turned into centres of excellence. He called for a revision and up-gradation of curricula, examination reforms and promotion of a culture of excellence and stressed that programmes must be periodically evaluated, based on industry trends and emphasis should be on research and innovation.

But in our country, mostly state universities do not care to revise the curriculum periodically. The pace at which knowledge and information is multiplying warrants the regular update of syllabi. People from diverse fields like administrators, managers, engineers, doctors, librarians, scientists, accountants, lawyers and artists having practical knowledge should be encouraged to work for universities so that regular up-gradation of syllabus can be executed as per the demand of industry.

Contractual Appointments in Teaching

In the “UGC regulations for higher education 2010”, it is clearly mentioned that the teachers should be appointed on contract basis only when it is absolutely necessary and in case student-teacher ratio does not satisfy the laid down norms. The fixed emoluments paid to such contract teachers should not be less than the monthly gross salary of a regularly appointed Assistant Professor. Such appointments should not be made initially for more than one academic session.

However, for the last few years, a trend has been started in teaching profession to appoint contractual staff on fixed salary between Rs.5000-20000 and job depends upon the mercy of Head of the Department. There are thousands of contractual teachers who are working in different universities since last so many years with the hope of getting regular appointments. If a teacher does not get job surety, how he/she can be expected to teach the students with full intellectual potential and calibre.

Appointment of contractual teaching staff is also a new breed of corruption in this profession. The obvious motive is to unfairly place the contract appointees for regular selections and it is obvious that vested interests are involved. If the government

has decided to follow the contractual appointment system, the terms and conditions must be clear. We have enough talent in our country; it is primarily the question of providing them an encouraging and respectful academic system.

Teaching without research

Faculty members, whether in schools, colleges, or universities, must be capable and talented and they must also be interested in teaching and research both. If we look at Indian universities, the mandate of most universities is to just teaching without research. As a result, their output in terms of research is small. Recently, government has set up a committee to create a framework for evaluation of research and rankings by promoting healthy competition among institutions, departments and individual researchers.

The move follows a disappointing performance by India's higher educational institutions in world rankings this year. The 18-member committee to improve research performance of academic institutions will be chaired by K. Vijay Raghavan, Secretary, Department of Biotechnology, and will submit a report within three months. But it is a big question, whether there will be any fruitful result of this committee like many other committees in higher education.

Time consuming recruitment process

It is common among higher educational institutions, whether it may be central or state universities, or any centrally funded other autonomous bodies, to remain headless for a long time after the incumbent demits office. Therefore, it is needed to have collegiums of scholars to select the head for these institutions. In the absence of regular head of the institutions many important decision could not be taken by the officiating head. There should also be a time-bound recruitment process of three to six months for all teaching posts. It has been noted that if personal interests are involved then the recruitment process is completed within a month; otherwise, it takes more than a year and in some cases it has also been seen that institutions advertise the posts again and again till their favourite person is selected.

In India, there is no agency to audit as to how many times the institution has advertised the post, how much amount has been spent on these advertisements, whether the post is filled up or not. On the name of autonomy, the heads of these institutions are wasting valuable tax-payers money. It has also been seen that when any teacher retires, there is no seriousness to fill the vacancy at the earliest. If appointment on many prominent posts (like CJI, CVC, CIC, CEC, Cabinet Secretary etc.) can be done well in advance before the person retires, then why not for faculty.

Selection of Non-academic Head of the Institutions

It has also been observed that there is lack of efficient leadership in nurturing our universities. If there is a mediocre person at the highest position in the university, then the system would be polluted. Vice-Chancellor from IAS, IPS and defence background cannot make good academics. When such persons are appointed in the universities, the whole system collapses. These institutions only cater to admission, examination, revaluation, re-examination, and distribution of degrees. They do not care much about teaching and research.

In recent years, it has been observed that persons from non-academic background are selected on the basis of 'political consideration' as Vice-chancellor and Directors by violating the norms and qualification as prescribed by UGC. Such types of person are appointed to implement political agenda of respective political party in education.

Recently teachers of Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI) wrote to the President Pranab Mukherjee, who is also the visitor of the university, requesting him to appoint "an academician of high repute and integrity" as the next vice-chancellor of the university in conformity with the qualifications for the appointment of V-Cs as prescribed by the University Grants Commission (UGC).

Quality of Doctoral Research (PhD)

Poor research output is considered as one of the biggest drawbacks of Indian higher education system. There are many causes for deteriorating

quality of the PhDs in India. In 2002 more than 1500 PhD theses were submitted within four months in various universities in India due to exemption in NET for Lectureship for those who submit their theses on or before 31st December 2002. Again in 2009, UGC extend this rule and exemption has been given for PhD holder from UGC-NET exam.

After 2009, there is boom in number of PhDs awarded by Indian universities (see Table 1). On one side, UGC has made strict rules in government universities for doing PhD where coursework and entrance test is necessary, whereas on the other side, it has opened the door for undeserving and mediocre persons for doing PhDs from private universities.

In India, PhD has become easiest degree to earn from most of the private universities. In these universities, there are no screening tests and interviews, no coursework, and no rigorous assessment of research work, just a Master's degree in hand and a pre-determined waiting period will

lead you to a doctorate. It's now an open secret that anyone can virtually buy a PhD degree. You just need to pay two/three lakh rupees to the right person.

In some universities, registration, coursework, thesis and *viva-voice* are all effectively managed. There are many universities which do not have adequate infrastructure and faculty for even postgraduate-level teaching, but have been offering PhDs. Most of these universities target students who fail to get a place in premier institutions.

Recently, we have seen the case of one of the private university of Meghalaya. In one year, it has awarded more than 400 PhDs. If we investigate the number and quality of PhDs awarded by private institutions, we will find many irregularities. Our educational planners are happy to see the quantitative growth in number of PhDs awarded by the Indian universities between 2008-09 and 2011-12. But, the real question is that has anybody tried to check the quality of these theses?

Table 1: Faculty-wise Number of Doctorate Degrees (Ph.D.) Awarded from in 2007-2011

S.No	Faculty	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11
1	Arts	4405	3496	4862	5037
2	Science	4514	3603	4619	5232
3	Commerce /Management	873	724	980	1259
4	Education	425	403	588	645
5	Engineering/Technology	1427	1141	1449	1682
6	Medicine	277	298	386	601
7	Agriculture	664	427	652	586
8	Veterinary Science	123	93	162	165
9	Law	127	152	146	220
10	Others	402	444	633	666
	Total	13237	10781	14477	16093

Arts: includes Humanities, Social Sciences, and Languages etc. Science : includes Home-Science, Computer Science and Computer Application. Education: includes Vidya Varidhi,

VachaspatiMedicine: includes Ayurveda, Dentistry, Homeopathy, Nursing, Pharmacy, Public Health/ Social Preventive Medicine, Unani, Tibbia, Physiotherapy, Occupational Therapy and Siddha

Medicine etc. Others: includes Library and Information Science, Music, Performing/Visual Arts, Journalism & Mass Communication, Physical Education and Social Work etc.

Source: UGC Annual Report of 2008-09; 2009-10; 2011-12

Quality of Research Papers and Articles

After the implementation of API/PBAS by UGC for evaluation of performance of faculty for career advancement and recruitment, a trend has emerged in the last five years to start an in-house journal within the organization, or by individual association and non-government organisation. In 2007, there were 5147 journals registered in India as per ISSN register whereas this number reached 13851 in 2012 (see Table 2). In many Indian universities, for the selection of faculty the research journals are classified into national and international for allotting

the marks. While quantifying these values by non-technical persons, many times a journal having word “International” is treated as foreign publication and it gets more marks. An influential person can get his or her paper published easily, whether it has any novelty or not. People with little experience in a particular field become expert referees. Plagiarism is rising day by day in education system. We have seen many prominent persons in the field of education who have been caught in this act. The ‘copy/cut and paste’ tendencies have increased the plagiarism activity. And there are several ‘cottage – industry journals’ which publish anything that is in type form, but who is to blame. Therefore, we should have a strict code of conduct for editors and referees. Therefore, while evaluating the quality of publications, emphasis should be given to those publications which are indexed and cited by international databases like SCOPUS, Web of Knowledge etc.

Table 2: Number of Journals Registered as per ISSN Record (from 2007 to 2012)

Year	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
No. of Journals Registered	5145	6400	7425	9119	11425	13851

Source: ISSN Registrar (www.issn.org)

Disparity in Budget Allocation

The UGC has been providing grants to Central and Deemed Universities, both under Plan (Development) and Non-plan (Maintenance) schemes while assistance to State Universities is being made available only under Plan (Development) Schemes. Under General Plan Development Assistance, the UGC assists each eligible University for the overall development covering the aspects namely, enhancing access, ensuring equity, imparting relevant education, improving quality and excellence, making their University administration more effective, providing more Faculty Improvement Programmes,

enhancing facilities for students, augmenting research facilities and any other plans of the University.

In order to fulfil these objectives, the financial assistance to meet the requirements of the University in terms of infrastructure, staff, equipment, books & journals, library etc. can be provided by the UGC under the General Plan Development Grant. But, it has been seen that there is much disparity in allocation of budget to different universities which is also one of important reason of degradation of the universities.

Table 3 & 4 shows the five highest and five least allocated budget to different universities under plan and non-plan allocation in the year 2011-12 by UGC.

Table 3: Plan grants paid to Central Universities in 2011-12**OLD CENTRAL UNIVERSITIES**

Highest allocated budget Universities	Rs. in Crore	Least allocated budget Universities	Rs. In Crore
Indira Gandhi National Tribal University	95.02	Maulana Azad National Urdu University	5.20
University of Hyderabad	80.33	The English & Foreign Languages University	24.00
University of Delhi	75.87	University of Allahabad	25.25
Jamia Millia Islamia	63.94	Aligarh Muslim University	34.20
Pondicherry University	63.84	Mahatma Gandhi Antarrashtriya Hindi Vishwavidyalaya	37.15

CENTRAL UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH-EASTERN REGION (NER)

Tezpur University	63.00	Rajiv Gandhi University	13.75
Mizoram University	42.13	Sikkim University	20.00
North-Eastern Hill University	39.60	Tripura University	22.25
Manipur University	34.97	Nagaland University	26.25
Assam University	32.95		

NEW CENTRAL UNIVERSITIES

Central University of Rajasthan	107.00	Central University of Himachal Pradesh	10.00
Central University of Karnataka	100.00	Central University of Jammu	11.50
Central University of Tamil Nadu	98.00	Central University of Kerala & Punjab	25.00 (each)
HNB Garhwal University, Uttrakhand	91.80	Central University of Gujarat	30.00
Dr HS Gaur University, MP	69.47	Central University of Orissa	35.00

Source: UGC Annual Report 2011-2012, pp.82-83.

Table 4 Non-Plan grants paid to Central Universities in 2011-12

Highest Least allocated budget Universities	Rs. in Crore	Least allocated budget Universities	Rs. In Crore
Banaras Hindu University (including Institute of Medical Sciences)	559.17	Mahatma Gandhi Antarrashtriya Hindi Vishwavidyalaya	8.83
Aligarh Muslim University (including J.N. Medical College)	545.22	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University	13.15

University of Delhi (including University College of Medical Science)	390.83	MaulanaAzad National Urdu University	20.13
Jawaharlal Nehru University	201.14	Rajiv Gandhi University	21.78
Jamia Millia Islamia	165.62	Tripura University	22.50

Source: UGC Annual Report 2011-2012, pp.86-87.

Too Many Regulatory Bodies

Presently, most of the educational regulators like AICTE, NCTE, DEC, MCI etc. (see Table 5) are entrusted to regulate the institutions of higher education and also to overlook the other norms. These regulators were envisioned to play a role of a catalyst regulatory body catering to the burgeoning manpower needs of the Indian economy. Instead of fulfilling these roles, these regulators have become ‘*Kamdhenu*’ cow for the nexus of corrupt politicians, bureaucrats, academicians and businessmen helping each other in making quick money through setting up more and more institutions. All norms for infrastructure, faculty, and curriculum have been flouted. These regulators have given licenses to set up thousands of institutions

without any reference to the actual manpower needs of various professions.

In recent years, we have seen that number of senior authorities of these regulatory bodies have been arrested due to involvement in corruption. One of the core questions is that “Whether the colleges affiliated to University are obliged to take separate permission/approval from these regulators to run a course.

Professor Yashpal Committee (2009) had suggested the integration of various statutory bodies related to education into one agency i.e., “The National Commission for Higher Education and Research (NCHER)”. Constitution of one apex body can facilitate better governing of the institutions of higher education. However, no concrete step has been taken to implement this recommendation of the report.

Table 5: Major Regulatory bodies in India

S.No	Regulator	Year of Estb.	Area
1	Indian Nursing Council (INC)	1947	Nursing Education
2	Dental Council of India (DCI)	1948	Dental Education
3	Pharmacy Council of India (PCI)	1948	Pharmacy Education
4	Medical Council of India (MCI)	1956	Medical Education
5	The Bar Council of India (BCI)	1961	Law Education & Practice
6	Central Council for Indian Medicine (CCIM)	1970	Education in Indian Systems of Medicine
7	The Council of Architecture (COA)	1972	Architectural education and registration
8	Central Council of Homeopathy (CCH)	1973	Homeopathic Medicine
9	Veterinary Council of India (VCI)	1984	Veterinary Education
10	Distance Education Council (DEC)	1985	Open and Distance Education
11	All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE)	1987	Technical Education

12	The Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI)	1992	Rehabilitation and Special Education
13	National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE)	1993	Teacher Education

Source: <http://www.ugc.ac.in/page/Professional-Councils.aspx>

Proliferation of Open & Distance Learning (ODL) Institutions

Higher education sector has grown significantly in scale and size but it is still unable to meet the growing demands because of many reasons including resource constraints. It is not possible to meet this rising demand through the capital-intensive conventional system of education only. The need for an alternative strategy to supplement the conventional system of higher education has been appreciated and accepted long back by the policy makers of the country.

Through various policy and programme interventions, attempts have been made to promote Open and Distance Learning (ODL) system to facilitate the expansion of higher education sector for the fulfillment of aspirations of those who are deprived of pursuing it for whatever reason.

In the initial phase of Distance Learning, no regulatory framework outside the University system was envisaged. The institutional arrangements and delivery mechanism for the programmes were devised and developed internally by the universities on its own through respective Statutory Bodies like Academic Council and Executive Council. Later on, when the number of institutions offering correspondence courses started increasing, the University Grants Commission in 1978-79, with a view to maintaining high standards, prescribed certain guidelines for starting correspondence courses.

In 1985, the UGC in exercise of the powers conferred by clause (f) of sub-section (1) of section 26 of the University Grants Commission Act, 1956 came out with the detailed regulations for maintenance of standards of instructions for the grant of the first degree through Non-Formal/Distance Education system. These Regulations applied to all first degrees in the faculties of Arts, Humanities, Fine Arts, Music, Social Sciences, Commerce and Sciences. The UGC also notified rules in 1988 to determine the fitness for grants to Open Universities imparting education exclusively through distance education in any branch or branches of knowledge.

In order to keep pace with the growing demand for recognition of ODL programmes, the DEC in the year 2007, decided to accord institutional recognition instead of programme specific recognition on the assumption that the appropriate academic bodies of universities/institutions would take care of the quality of education imparted. On the basis of approval of DEC, many universities / institutions started technical education programmes without the approval of the concerned regulator like AICTE, NCTE etc.

A large number of them “misused” the opportunity for commercialization of ODL system through unregulated expansion disregarding standards of education. The proliferation of such ODL Institutions are the main reason for deterioration of Indian education system, which are behaving like degree dispensing mills and has also affected the credibility and acceptability of such programmes adversely (see Table 6).

Table 6: Year-wise Growth of ODL Institutions in India

Year	Dual Mode Universities/ Institutes	Single Mode Open Universities	Total Distance Education Institutions
1962	1	-	1
1975	22	-	22

1982	34	1	35
1985	38	2	40
1990	46	5	51
2000	70	9	79
2005	106	13	119
2010	242	14	256

Source: <http://www.ugc.ac.in/deb/pdf/growthDEB.pdf>

Clash between Professional versus Support staff

In the development and progress of any educational institution, each and every staff has an important role whether it may be academic, non-academic or ministerial. Everybody should make one's optimum contribution. Unfortunately, there is always clash between Professional versus Support staff in almost all educational institutions in our country.

It may be teacher or scientist, they think that they are superior to the other staff and due to their emergence other supportive staffs are working in the organization. But they should realize that in any organization academics and administrative set-up work in tandem. Nobody is supplement to anyone. Both are complementary to each other and admittedly they should realize each other's importance in the effective functioning and growth of organization.

Conclusion

Getting a place in global ranking is a matter of pride for any educational institutions. Degradation of the Indian education system warrants a revival of intellectual convention. The malaise is deep-rooted and needs serious thinking and a complete overhaul of the India education system. It is high time for our policy makers to formulate a comprehensive plan for the educational institutions to meet global standards.

But, before taking any decision, a proper evaluation of the existing system is warranted. The government is investing huge amount of resources in higher education. The effort to increase 'quantity'

exponentially must be matched with commensurate efforts to improve 'quality'. We must lead our institutions into the ranks of the best global institutions.

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